

Field efficacy of NSB, NSKE, or an insecticide on mungbean insect pests and yield and benefit:cost ratio at Imbunia, Jaen, Nueva Ecija and Baloc Santo Domingo, Nueva Ecija, Philippines.^a Jan-Mar 1988.

Treatment	Leaves folded ^b (no./m ²)		Pods damaged ^c (%)		Grain yield (kg/ha)		Difference ^d (kg/ha) (T-C)		Value of increased yield (\$)		Cost of treatment (\$)		Benefit:cost ratio	
	Imbunia	Baloc	Imbunia	Baloc	Imbunia	Baloc	Imbunia	Baloc	Imbunia	Baloc	Imbunia	Baloc	Imbunia	Baloc
NSB, 5000 ppm	18 a	24 b	11 a	22 b	817 b	589 b	103	244	73	173	6	8	12:1	22:1
NSKE, 3%	15 a	11 a	11 a	20 ab	853 b	643 b	139	298	99	212	16	20	6:1	11:1
Monocrotophos, 0.3 kg ai/ha	23 a	21 b	14 a	16 a	1001 a	1110 a	287	765	204	543	34	44	6:1	12:1
Water (control)	35 b	24 b	22 b	34 c	714 b	345 b	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. Av of 6 replications. ^bBy *Sylepta* sp. and *Lamprosema* sp. of LFs. ^cBy *Etiella* sp., *Maruca* sp., and *Heliothis* sp. of pod borers. ^dT = treatment, C = control.

and *Heliothis* sp. was assessed at two priming stages.

At Imbunia, LF damage was reduced significantly in plots treated with NSB, KSKE, and insecticide (see table). At Baloc, NSKE treatment was

significantly superior to NSB or insecticide. Pod borer damage was significantly reduced by NSB, NSKE, and insecticide at both Imbunia and Baloc.

Mungbean grain yield was highest in plots treated with insecticide, followed by those in neem-treated plots. The benefit:cost ratio was highest for treatment with NSB. □

Parasitization of the Malayan black bug (MBB) by five species of egg parasitoids

G. S. Arida, B. M. Shepard, and V. A. Perez, IRRI

The ability of a parasitoid to cause high parasitization in the presence of competing species may determine its effectiveness as a natural control agent.

At Palawan National Agricultural College (PNAC), Aborlan, Palawan, we studied the control of MBB *Scotinophara coarctata* by the

indigenous egg parasitoid *Telenomus triptus* and four introduced species: *T. cyrus*, *Trissolcus basalis*, *Psix lacunatus*, and *T. chloropus*.

One gravid female of each parasitoid species was introduced into individual 11- × 55-cm mylar cages with potted plants bearing a female MBB with 1 egg

mass. After 24 h, the egg masses were removed and held in 1.5- × 15-cm test tubes plugged with cotton until parasites or MBB nymphs emerged. The experiment was replicated 20 times.

More than 90% of the parasites that emerged were the indigenous *T. triptus* (see figure). □

Egg parasitization (%)

Parasitization of MBB eggs by 5 species of egg parasitoids. IRRI, 1988.

Effect of conidia germination on infection of brown planthopper (BPH) by insect fungi

M. C. Rombach, *Insect Pathology Resource Center, Boyce Thompson Institute for Plant Research*; R. M. Aguda, *Entomology, Department, IRRI*; and D. W. Roberts, *Boyce Thompson Institute for Plant Research, Tower Road, Ithaca, NY 14853, USA*

Conidia of insect fungi actively invade BPH. After a conidium lands on the insect cuticle, germination takes about 8 to 16 h, depending on the temperature and relative humidity.

After the germination tube is formed, the conidium produces specific chitinase enzymes to dissolve the insect cuticle.

This allows the fungus to enter the insect body cavity, where further fungus

growth occurs. At the end of the infection cycle, the mycelium sporulates on the outside of the insect.

Conidia produced on the cadaver can infect healthy BPH initiating epizootics of the fungus.

We tested whether germination of conidia before application will hasten the infection process, and increase BPH mortality. We also tested whether incubation of insects at saturated relative humidity (RH) for 2 h directly after application aids germination and increases BPH mortality.

A strain of the fungus *Beauveria bassiana* (Bals.) Vuill.—ARSEF 714, isolated from BPH—was grown on Sabouraud Dextrose agar. After 2 wk of incubation at 25-28°C, conidia were washed off the plate in a 0.02% Tween 80 solution and counted by standard hemocytometer techniques. Dextrose at